

Quantum Mechanics From Inertia Transforming Into Independent E and p Values? Part 2

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In Part 1, we argued that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ contains E and p which are physically different types of interaction variables. We argued that nature must somehow keep E and p independent in $-Et+px$ (if nature also respects this Lorentz invariant). As a result, we suggested a math function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which actually acts like a probability in terms of products and ensures conservation of E and p.

Here, we wish to consider the situation from a different viewpoint. Like in Part 1, we do not postulate a priori any probability. Rather, we argue that there exist interactions in nature which conserve both E and p (elastic collisions) and that these two interaction variables are associated with different physical processes. For example, the notion of action-reaction is enough to see conservation of momentum, but conservation of energy is an independent process. In other words, E is like an enhanced inertia (m_0 and v), while p is like a moving inertia. An interaction which conserves both is complicated, yet we argue that the notion of the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ should still hold for two interacting particles.

For a single particle, the center-of-mass moves as $x=vt$ and so one would expect that t and x in $-Et+px$ are correlated. If one has two particles coming together to interact, then by conservation of E,p one has E_1+E_2 and p_1+p_2 (one dimension), but x and t for the two particles should be the same and it seems that one is not concerned about $x=vt$. Furthermore, a given outcome of the interaction E_3+E_4 and p_3+p_4 must also be linked to $-Et+px$ and there must be conservation of total E and p. Thus: $-(-E_3-E_4+E_1+E_2) t + (-p_3-p_4+p_1+p_2) x = 0$. This suggests mathematically that t and x are independent variables in direct contrast to $x=vt$. Furthermore, the system must somehow ensure that x and t are independent for any E_i, E_j and p_i, p_k such that $E_i+E_j=E_1+E_2$ and $p_i+p_j = p_1+p_2$ as this is all the information that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ displays. Given that E and p are linked with different interactions, we suggest that there must exist an a priori property of a particle which allows for the above considerations. This would then explain how any $E_i+E_j=E_1+E_2$ and $p_i+p_j = p_1+p_2$ holds. In Part 1, we argued that this condition may occur if a particle is associated with fluctuating x and t values in terms of interactions given by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. The center-of-mass still moves as $x=vt$, but in an interaction it is the interaction process which is key, not the particle center-of-mass. One requires a description of such an interaction which can handle both E and p and is consistent with whatever information special relativity allows. We suggest that the $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is such a description, but that it carries the notion of periodicity in space and time and that this periodicity is then linked with E and p. This then becomes associated with Planck's constant to link periodicity to E,p.

Deterministic Physics

Newtonian mechanics is deterministic, yet it introduces the idea of conservation of energy and momentum and also the two distinct notions of p and kinetic energy. P (momentum) may be associated with a force linked with inertia and its speed whereas kinetic energy is something different. As a result, target hits are often associated with changes in momentum and impulse,

while motion in a vertical constant gravitational field is linked with a loss of energy. In other words, we argue that Newtonian mechanics introduces a number of key ideas for the development of free particle quantum mechanics.

Special Relativity

Special relativity produces explicit equations for E and p, i.e.

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((1b))$$

It also yields the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + px \quad \text{which is linked with } x=vt \text{ motion} \quad ((2))$$

Again, E and p represent different kinds of physical interactions and so it might seem surprising to see them both in the same Lorentz invariant expression ((2)), especially given $x=vt$. Physically, they act differently and are associated with different kinds of conservation as p is always conserved, but only total energy, not necessarily ((1a)) is conserved. ((1a)) is conserved in elastic collisions.

Given special relativity, just as in the case of Newtonian mechanics, one must impose conservation of energy and momentum by hand.

The question we ask is the following. What happens when two particles collide elastically? In such a case, one has:

$$\text{Initial } E_1, E_2 \quad \text{and} \quad p_1, p_2 \quad (\text{one dimension}) \quad ((3a))$$

For the sake of argument, assume that one knows a specific outcome, so as not to introduce any notion of probability, i.e.

$$E_3, E_4 \quad \text{and} \quad p_3, p_4 \quad ((3b))$$

The point we make is that during this interaction two very different mechanisms occur, one which ensures conservation of momentum and the other, conservation of energy. We argue that these are independent. For example, using the notion of action-reaction it is easy to see conservation of momentum, but that does not predict that particle energy is conserved. In some cases sound may be created etc.

We suggest that one must consider a scheme in which the relativistic Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ is respected even for a combined E_1, E_2 and p_1, p_2 particle. In such a case, one completely ignores the interaction mechanics, but respects conservation and the Lorentz invariant, i.e. writes:

$$-(E_1 + E_2) t + (p_1 + p_2) x \quad ((4))$$

The same x and t appear for each particle and even though $x=v_1t$ and $x=v_2t$ for each particle separately, it seems that the combination ((4)) is not based on any consideration of $x=vt$ motion. It is rather about an interaction. This means that one expects that:

$$-(E_3-E_4+E_1+E_2)t + (-p_3-p_4+p_1+p_2)x = 0 \quad ((5))$$

The Lorentz invariant should be linked to both E and p conservation and this implies that t and x should be independent variables. At the very least, this means one does not consider any $x=vt$ type motion. We note that there is also no notion of probability in ((5)).

The next consideration is that $-Et+px$ holds in ((5)) with x and t independent and so should also hold for $-Et+px$. In the unusual scenario, $x=vt$ for a single particle, but we argue that one should also be able to consider an independent x and t in this case as well in order to be consistent with ((5)). The question becomes: How can one possibly have x and t independent for a single particle? Certainly $x=vt$ is a correct equation for the center-of-mass. As argued in previous notes, one may consider probabilistic fluctuations in the time and position of interaction. There is no a priori reason to constrain the force to the center-of-mass as is done in Newtonian mechanics. There, an interaction must occur in $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$ and so everything is essentially condensed to a point.

We suggest that conservation of E, p and the enforcement of $-Et+px$, even for two interacting particles, leads to the notion of

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \text{ for a single particle with } x \text{ and } t \text{ fluctuating independently (probabilistically with } x \text{ not= } vt \text{)} \quad ((6))$$

Products of ((6)), together with x, t fluctuating independently allow for conservation of energy and p , which are physically different.

As a result, the inherent probability of a quantum free particle comes from insisting that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, applied to two interacting particles, is the physical source of conservation of momentum and energy. This means that x and t must be physically independent and we postulate that this occurs through probabilistic fluctuations in interaction hits, already at single particle level. As argued in Part 1, this is the manner in which to keep E and p independent in $-Et+px$, as this Lorentz invariant must still apply to two particles interacting and be consistent with conservation of E and p .

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part 1, we argued that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ contains two very different interaction variables, E and p . P (momentum) is linked with inertia and velocity, i.e. one must stop both, while E is like an enhanced inertia. They apply in different kinds of analysis, yet appear together in the same Lorentz invariant. We thus argued that there must be a physical mechanism to keep them independent and suggested that x and t represent probabilistic fluctuations in $-Et+px$, such that impulse hits or energy interactions are linked with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

Here, we try to examine this idea more closely. We suggest that $-Et+px$ holds for a single particle for which $x=vt$. Two such particles, however, may interact elastically in which case both

E and p are conserved. We argue that $-(E_1+E_2)t + (p_1+p_2)x$ (p in one dimension) should be respected in such a case. In order to remove probabilistic considerations, we assume that the outcome is E_3, E_4 and p_3, p_4 such that: $-(-E_3-E_4+E_1+E_2)t + (-p_3-p_4+p_1+p_2)x = 0$. This means that x and t must be independent and not linked with any $x=vt$. If this is the case, this independence should also apply to $-Et+px$ for a single particle. Usually one has $-Et+px$ and $x=vt$ which is fine for the center-of-mass, but we suggest that a second principle exists simultaneously, namely that x and t become physically independent if they represent probabilistic fluctuations related to the actual interaction (and not cm motion). In such a case, one may apply $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ to a single free particle with x and t representing interaction x,t values and $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ being a complex probability. This then ensures conservation of both energy and momentum (two independent conservations) when product probabilities are taken.